

SCOTTISH
SLAVONIC
REVIEW

A twice-yearly publication on
the literatures, languages,
history, cultures and the
arts in Eastern Europe

Special Issue: Russian Modernism

14

SPRING 1990

Department of Russian
University of St Andrews

FATAL HEARTS OF THE 1920s
(ON MIKHAIL BULGAKOV'S STORY *THE HEART OF A DOG*)

Zsuzsa Hetényi

(Translated by Jonathan Crossan)

Beware of dogs, beware of evil workers. . .
Philippians 3. 2.

Bulgakov's story *The Heart of a Dog* (*Sobach'e serdtse*) emerged from semi-oblivion in 1987 and has since taken the bookstalls and the theatre in the Soviet Union by storm. Its fate cannot be compared with that of the novel *The Master and Margarita*, of course, for *The Heart of a Dog* has been translated into many languages and printed in Russian in France, yet it is only now that it has been repatriated and become accessible to those whom it most concerns.¹

The Heart of a Dog is the third part of Bulgakov's satirical trilogy of the mid-1920s. The first two parts, *The Diaboliad* (*D'yavoliada*) and *The Fatal Eggs* (*Rokovye yaytsa*) managed to see the light of day during the author's lifetime, but this story was not so lucky. In her engaging and meticulous biography of Bulgakov, Marietta Chudakova describes in detail how it was confiscated by the NKVD, and she quotes *inter alia* L. B. Kamenev's opinion of the story: 'A keen lampoon on modern life which can under no circumstances be printed' ('Ostryy pamflet na sovremennost', pechatat' ni v koem sluchae nel'zya.').² The present article seeks to examine where the 'keen lampoonery' of this work lies, at what levels and in what particular details of plot and genre it is manifest, and how it acquires a philosophical meaning.

The action of the story is classically symmetrical in structure and moves speedily and straightforwardly towards its dénouement. In the middle a fateful transplant operation is performed, occupying a central position between the first operation, during which the Professor heals the dog's flank, and the third operation, which results in the re-establishment of the initial situation. The story's headlong pace is the

result of elements at the satirical level. Maximal use is made of such stock comic effects as the speech patterns of the characters, who each represent one stratum of society. This demonstrates clearly that a dramatic version was in the author's mind even before he completed the story, as does the fact that, if we discount the first chapter, the story observes unity of place: it is staged like an indoor game. Appearing in it we have the proletarian, both politically conscious and politically unconscious, the party initiate and the naive party novice, the post-NEPman and the vulgar Philistine, a servant, a housemaid, people from the street (a typist, a janitor), an 'aristocratic' professor and a 'non-aristocratic' intellectual. The contrast between this broad spectrum of social types and the dog's class-orientated vision of the same society is rich in possibilities for satirical comparison and analysis.

The animal's disengaged and all-knowing view is a typical ploy of satirical genres. In Bulgakov's story the comedy of the situation is complicated by the comic nature of a character who represents a new form of creature: a mixture of dog and human being. (True, the suggestion is there that the dog and the man Chugunkin bear a primordial resemblance: both obey the principle that you sit up and beg where the pickings are richer.) This variety of comic style, as we shall see later, can give rise to complex allegorical juxtapositions. A distinctive, if not too unusual form of comedy is also displayed in the depiction of the gulf which separates the world of the Professor from the world of 'the rest' (and this is not to be interpreted in a political sense, as has been done by V. Lakshin in his foreword to the first Soviet publication of the story, where he suspects the Professor of being alienated from the people).³ Stress is laid on his different values, his different way of life and even the distinctive details of his apartment.

The *fantastic* elements are corroborated in the spirit of the Gogolian tradition. The documentary-style genres of diary and newspaper articles are used, while at the same time the most improbable gossip is introduced, when the new 'person' makes his appearance in town. At the very end of the story — following the logic of the genre — there is a general covering of tracks, when the facts themselves are thrown into question (cf. the expressions: 'afterwards the neighbours said', 'they were even supposed to have seen', 'it is difficult to be certain', 'Zina jabbered that the doctor's face was apparently quite green', 'well anyhow, the girl could have been lying. . .', p.205). Bormental' is alleged to have burnt the blue notebook in which he wrote down the history of Sharik-Sharikov's illness and whose contents form the first

half of Chapter 5. This is permissible according to the internal logic of the plot, but it leaves the reader puzzled: how then could this diary possibly have served later on as the material for the story? Similar tricks of verification and dubiousness, deriving from the best traditions of Russian fantasy, force the reader to transport his thoughts onto another plane and detach himself from direct observations rooted in any concrete society.

The plot of *The Heart of a Dog* may be understood most easily as an allegory, and more particularly as a *political allegory*. The surgical operation, which is a violent intervention in the processes of nature, should be understood as an allegory of the Revolution, a forceful interference in the processes of history (cf. the work of other authors, like Pasternak and Kabakov).⁴ This 'operation on society' is being performed on the Russian people, who correspond in the story to the stray dog, picked up off the street, and to Klim Chugunkin, who is also picked up off the street, but dead . . . It proves impossible to create a creature from them which meets the Professor's ideals. It is also worth recalling that Dr Bormental', too, was effectively 'picked up off the street' by the Professor — he, too, only really begins to develop under the control of the Professor, who has taken him under his wing both at the University and at the flat. The operation performed on this loyal, but as yet insufficiently confident pupil is supposed to leap a few stages of natural development. It was just these kinds of task which the 1917 Revolution had set itself with respect to history, and the text of the story speaks openly about such stages of development.⁵ The inorganic development brought about by the Revolution is not simply placed in opposition to Evolution (the one thing that Bulgakov accepted, judging by his famous letter to the Soviet Government),⁶ but is completely invalidated as an act which will inevitably end in tragedy and which must be made never to have happened.

The story concerns an experimental laboratory-revolution conceived theoretically by an intellectual, the Professor, in a way not dissimilar to the conceiving of the Russian Revolution of 1917, which was the first in the world to wish to put the theory of Socialism into practice. This revolution was led by the intelligentsia, a group of professional revolutionaries, many of whom lacked sufficient knowledge of the Russia of the time, but who were erudite in the theory of Marxism.⁷ This aspect of the allegory gives rise to the thought that, when a theory of society defines and then outstrips actual practice, i.e. becomes divorced from real-life options, then a tragic outcome, or at least

failure, becomes inevitable. The accepted wisdom that 'a creature can get out of its creator's control' is reflected in the Jewish legends of Golem, whom we would be justified in comparing with Sharikov. The Golem of Prague rebelled and defiled the Holy Sabbath, and therefore the Rabbi Löw, his creator, destroyed him. Yet another homunculus, the Golem of the Polish Rabbi Elijah, collapsed on its creator as it was being destroyed and crushed him.⁸

Bulgakov's story would seem to permit a more concrete interpretation of this allegory, the key to which lies in the ambivalent figure of the Professor. Like the other figures in the story, he has been conceived not as a psychologically plausible character, but rather as a formula, combining god and devil simultaneously in a single entity. These two motifs permeate the whole story.

The Professor's divine characteristics are, of course, closely associated with the fact that he is the creator of a new person (cf. his range of activities: rejuvenation, regeneration of people, creating Sharikov). The epithets used in this semantic field take on a concrete form only gradually, and often they appear in an ironic context. In the dog's eyes, for example, the Professor is a 'master' ('vlastitel', p.123), a miraculous vision; to it he becomes 'an important canine philanthropist' ('vazhnyy pesiy blagotvoritel', pp.125, 208), 'a benefactor' ('blagodetel', p.123). The first operation is represented as an act of death ('I'm on my way to paradise ['idu v rai]', p.129) and resurrection ('when he arose' ['kogda on voskres'], p.129) for the dog, an act performed by a creature to whom life and death are subordinate. The accent is soon shifted from the realm of the sacred to that of the superhuman (the Professor as magician, magus, sorcerer ['charodey', 'mag', 'kudesnik'], p.131), a motif which gains in importance when the same group of words are later put into the mouth of a human, rather than of a dog, when they are spoken by one of the patients who has been operated on, i.e. created, by the Professor. The description of this patient reveals a depth to the motif unusual in satirical writing: 'His face was pink in colour, like a baby's. He could not bend his left leg, so he had to drag it along the carpet, which made the right leg bob up and down like a child's jack-in-the-box'; 'in the buttonhole of his jacket a precious stone stood out like an eye'; '... his underpants were cream-coloured, embroidered with silk black cats, and they smelt of perfume' (p.131). On the one hand, the creature is pure, a fresh creation ('baby's', 'child's'), on the other it is demonic (the limp, an eye-like stone, black cats), thus in a certain sense foreshadowing the evil

direction taken by Sharikov's development. The duality of god and devil/demon is maintained in descriptions of the Professor's external appearance throughout the entire story. It is particularly graphic in the operation scene,⁹ where such epithets as 'sated vampire', 'tiger', 'robber', 'savage', 'crafty', and 'murderer' leave us in no doubt that this kind of deity is by no means a source of order in the world, even though it 'blesses the dog before its difficult venture' and places a 'red crown' on its forehead (pp.155-56). A similar displacement can be observed in the middle of the story where, in the key phrase of the diary 'Professor Preobrazhensky, you are a creator! (Blot)' ('Professor Preobrazhensky, vy — tvorets! (Klyaksa)', p.164), the final word in brackets cancels the preceding word.¹⁰

We must dwell here on the significance of the Professor's surname, Preobrazhensky (from *preobrazhenie* meaning transformation or transfiguration). This is a word which refers directly to the character's divine qualities, while at the same time semantically uniting death and birth and expressing rebirth, that is the destruction of one condition and the birth of a new one. Structural unity may be found in the fact that the dog first saw the light of day at the Preobrazhenskaya zastava (the Transfiguration Gate) and recalls that 'boundless sunny courtyard' as heaven (p.153); again, it is at the Preobrazhenskaya zastava that Klim Chugunkin dies from a stab in the heart (p.165). The coincidence of the Professor's name and this locus of birth and death confirms the conditionality (*uslovnost*) of the plot and of the Professor within it, in whom the spirit of good and the spirit of evil are combined. The same duality is also suggested by the details of his flat and his possessions. The dog arrives in the middle of paradise: 'Suddenly an unexpected light flashed on joyfully behind the pink glass door . . . a wave of divine warmth flowed over him, and the woman's skirt smelt of lilies of the valley' (p.127), although it is true to say that the other heavenly flower, the tulip in the lobby, is only an electric one. The Professor's fur coat emits sparks, and a gold chain sparkles on his stomach. A quite contrary description follows a mere page later, only to turn again into its antithesis — thereby giving the impression to the reader that a game is being played within the text. 'They both found themselves in a narrow, dimly lit corridor . . . they reached the end . . . and ended up in a dark closet, which the dog found momentarily distasteful because of its evil smell. The darkness split open and was transformed into blinding daylight, light flashed and shone from all sides . . .' (p.128). This is a black road which leads to hell, but there is a way back.

The author does not tire of creating time and again this atmosphere of duality around the sage of Prechistenka Street, all the while observing a strict balance. Whereas the plates in the flat are patterned with 'heavenly flowers', they nonetheless have to have 'a broad black border' (p.140). And whereas 'the table is as heavy as a tombstone', the napkins upon it are folded 'in the shape of papal tiaras' (ibid.). The deity carries a heavenly-sounding repeater watch around with him (p.146), but he also unexpectedly begins to emit 'an unpleasant blue smoke' (p.142). The spirit of black magic is guaranteed by the presence of an ominous owl (p.130) as well as of a fairy-tale black cat/familiar (p.175). The 'main department of paradise . . . the kingdom of the lady-cook' turns out by a familiar logic to be a 'terrible hell'.¹¹ (The strong colours used to describe the kitchen are also accompanied by irony: a fire burns on the hotplate, for example, yet Dar'ya Petrovna's suitor is a firefighter.)¹² The balance between these two lines is maintained even at a lexical level: there are frequent conversational passages containing such elements as: 'God!', 'Lord!' and 'hell', 'devil', 'demon' (*bog, bozhe, gospodi, chert, d'yavol, bes*); indeed, practically a whole dictionary could be composed from these expressions. (The same is true of *The Master and Margarita*). Bearing in mind that the words *bog* and *chert* are mostly interchangeable in such expressions (*bog znaet — chert znaet, bog s nim — chert s nim*, etc.), then the equal number of 'elevated' and 'base' words (about thirty in each group) would seem to be of some relevance.¹³ In view of this linguistic game there is no way of avoiding attempts to interpret proper names in the light of their original meanings either, e.g., by referring Prechistenka Street back to the notion of the Immaculate Conception, or by seeing Mertyvy pereulok as a road leading to death, an analogue to the dark corridor in the flat.

The operation itself with the birth of a new person has the features of an orgiastic mystery, as indicated above, but it is placed within the framework of the biblical story of the birth of Christ. The operation is performed on 23 December; over the next three days the dog undergoes a crisis, and then on 6 January — Epiphany, or the Feast of the Baptism of Christ — he speaks his first proper words,¹⁴ i.e. he symbolically enters the ranks of the human race. The diary abounds with biblical associations (e.g. numbers — Chugunkin expired at four minutes past four, the dog began to bark at twelve minutes past twelve, etc.). Chugunkin is also the same age as Yeshua in the novel *The Master and Margarita*, i.e. twenty-eight.¹⁵ Looking down on all the events

which the people interpret as signs of the end of the world, is a single star (pp.150, 208), recalling the Christmas Star or Star of Bethlehem. But the Christ motifs soon give way to a multifaceted description of a distinctive Lucifer in revolt against his benefactor. This fallen angel adopts particularly rebellious and dangerous behaviour after the scene in the bathroom, which would seem to perform the function of a worldwide flood in microcosm. After the destruction of 'the unclean spirit' (p.204) the return of the Christ motifs signals the restoration of worldwide order. 'The March fog gave the dog headaches in the mornings, especially around the circular scar on his skull' (p.208). The death of Sharikov the man and the rebirth of the dog, as well as the restoration of world order occur around Eastertime, a festival uniting death and birth — and the scar on the dog's head graphically symbolizes the marks of the Crown of Thorns.

Conclusions inevitably suggest themselves. There is no doubt that Bulgakov wanted to sow the idea that when a person pries into the secrets of nature (p.193), then tragedy follows. For in prying he imagines himself to be in charge of good and evil; he puts himself in the place of God or Satan. It would not be erroneous to suggest that we see here, especially in the ambivalent figure of the Professor, the premises of ideas which are given more detailed exposition later in the figure of Woland. While Woland is a force in the familiar Faustian sense, desiring Evil, yet doing Good,¹⁶ Preobrazhensky's duality inspires the opposite idea: he desires Good, yet does Evil. (Violence breeds violence . . .)

But such conclusions, by themselves, are insufficient.

Bulgakov quite clearly considers the Revolution a bloody interference in the course of history (we need only recall the bloody scene of the operation). He points out mistakes, the first of which is that the new system requires a leap forward in history on the part of strata of society which are quite unready for it. (It is interesting to note that Preobrazhensky's first aim was merely rejuvenation, yet it turned out that a far more fundamental leap forward was involved . . .) This thesis is well illustrated by Sharikov's residual canine characteristics. The way he chooses his fiancée by smell and because of their former gateway friendship demonstrates only the comic side of this mixture of character. His choice of occupation is quite horrifying, however: he works for the 'Moscow City Department for the Elimination of Stray Animals' ('otdel *ochistki* goroda Moskvy ot brodyachikh zhivotnykh',

p.198, my emphasis — Z.H.), which may be understood as referring to the party purge of the 1920s and the liquidation of 'stray' (unnecessary) elements of society. Suspicions are even further aroused by the leather jerkin, the leather breeches and the leather riding-boots which Sharikov wears. The *Chekisty* wore leather, and this leather clothing represents not only economic well-being, but also the possession of power. Sharikov's career, which takes him into the ranks of the 'organs', is simultaneously a return to an animal medium (leather) and to wild basic instincts (killing, receiving a piece of the kill in exchange for services rendered). Sharikov's external appearance reveals the link between power and brutality, with the following implication: the lower a person sinks, the higher he rises in that society, as indeed that society requires.

Bulgakov sees a second fatal mistake in the way that, in place of God (and traditional values), a new god is being established — Man himself. (For a reader in the 1980s it is easy to draw a comparison between the Professor and Lenin,¹⁷ or even Stalin — yet in 1925 Bulgakov could hardly have guessed how near the mark he would come with the name of his small-time crook, Chugunkin, a name which a few years later might be associated with Stalin in a 'counter-revolutionary' way).

The work's main allegorical meaning appears to go beyond this, however. Bulgakov seems to be dealing here with the new faith which teaches that Man is the Creator, who holds in his grasp both his own future and that of the planet; it is He who transforms nature, organic life, and above all society. This idea, which is not far removed from positivism, lay at the basis of the *Godbuilding* movement in Russia in the first decade of this century and, as such, came in for harsh criticism at the hands of Marxists-Leninists in the years 1908–10. In my view the idea arose in some form again after 1917 and was revealed, either directly or indirectly, in works by a number of writers in the 1920s, sometimes from sharply opposed positions.¹⁸ At the end of the story Bulgakov would seem to give nature (or history) a chance to resume its normal course. The final paragraphs, with their stubborn repetition of the word 'man', give cause for suspicion, however. The story has shown us very well what 'an important man' is capable of doing (p.208).¹⁹

NOTES

1. *Sobach'e serdtse* was published in the journal *Znanya*, 1987, No.6, pp.73–141 and reprinted in M. A. Bulgakov, *Sobranie sochineniy v pyati tomakh*, M., 1989–, vol.2, pp.119–208. Earlier it had appeared in *Grani*, No.69, 1968, pp.3–85, as an entire issue of *Student*, No.9/10, London, 1968 and as a separate book, Paris, 1969. Page references to vol.2 of the Soviet collected edition will be given in brackets in the text.
2. M. Chudakova, *Zhizneopisanie Mikhaila Bulgakova*, M., 1988, p. 252.
3. See *Znanya*, 1987, No.6, pp.73–76.
4. Cf Yury's words in *Doktor Zhivago*, Paris, 1959, p.226: 'What magnificent surgery! Putrid old ulcers skilfully removed in one go! A simple untrammelled verdict on eternal injustice which expects to be towed to . . .' Cf. also the words of the very 'Bulgakovian' hero of Aleksandr Kabakov's cinema-drama 'Nevozvrashchenets' (*Iskusstvo kino*, No.6, 1989, p.170): 'An aberration which has mortified this country for practically a century has been cured, cured in the only possible way — surgically . . . And you suppose you will survive the operation? And the operation itself, nice was it? Hospital surgery means blood, lumps of meat, fear, and no anaesthetic, mind . . . So is it really better to die all hacked about than a natural death?'
5. 'No-one can make that work, Doctor, least of all people whose development has lagged behind the Europeans by 200 years and who to this day still aren't quite sure how to button their own pants!' (p.145).
6. M. Bulgakov, *Chasha zhizni*, M., 1988, p.508.
7. Cf. M. Geller and A. Nekrich: *Utopiya u vlasti* 1, London, 1982, p.27: 'Except for a few weeks in 1905 Lenin had not been in Russia since 1900. "My thoughts will be somewhat theoretical," he stated, "but in general correct," confessed the leader of the Bolshevik Party.'
8. See the entry under 'Golem' in: Hans Biedermann, *Handlexikon der magischen Künste*, Graz, 1973.
9. Cf. the following characteristic passages: 'hawk-like nose' (p.135), 'his head shone (p.145), 'his words fell . . . like some muffled underground rumble' (p.145), 'lightning flashes distorted his face' (p.167), 'Filipp Filippovich acquired his final title to divinity . . . bursting in wearing a dark brown fox-fur coat, he shone with a million snow spangles . . . and his voice could be heard like a loudhailer all over the apartment' (pp.147–48). Or during the operation scene: 'The priest ['zhrets'] stood in a blaze of white . . . His close-cropped grey hair was hidden beneath a white cap, reminiscent of a patriarch's mitre; the deity was all in white and over the white, like a priest's stole, he wore a narrow rubber apron. His hands were in black gloves' (p.153). Ambivalent gestures are conveyed with preciseness of a scenario: the professor raises his hands as if to bless the dog, then his teeth clench together, he falls on the dog like a predator on its victim and begins to cut it up with his instruments.
10. There are quite a few other ironic counterpoints; cf. for example, p.145: 'Fortified by an ample meal, he would thunder like an ancient prophet, and his head shone like silver.'

11. The atmosphere of the kitchen is evoked in the following expressions: 'a flame raged'; 'crimson columns'; 'eternal fiery torment'; 'the kitchen gurgles and sputters in enclosed vessels'; 'Dar'ya cuts off the heads and claws of helpless grouse'; 'like an impassioned executioner, she ripped out the innards, she twisted something through the mincer'; 'the fire'; 'a terrible hell' (pp.149–50).
12. Cf. also the following dialogue between them: "You forced yourself on me like a demon," Dar'ya Petrovna muttered in the semidarkness. "Leave me alone! Zina will be here any minute . . ."

"What a fireball you are!" replied the black-moustached fireman hoarsely' (p.150).
13. *Черт*
 черт лохматый; ну вас к черту; на какого черта; черт его знает; черт знает что такое; к черту; к чертям; черт!; вот черт!; какого черта; с этим . . . как его . . . дьявола; на какого дьявола; с этим чертом; какой там черт; черт меня возьми; черти бы его съели; черт с ним.
Бог
 боже мой; богом клянусь; бог с вами; бог их знает; Боже вас сохрани; не дай Бог; Господи, благослови; Ей-Богу; Господи; Боже мой; ради бога; боже ты мой. (Repetitions not given)
14. For a different approach to this problem, see an article which came my way only after completion of the present work: Diana L. Burgin, 'Bulgakov's Early Tragedy of the Scientist-Creator: An Interpretation of The Heart of a Dog', *Slavic and East-European Journal*, vol. 22, No.4, 1978, pp.494–508.
15. This number is obviously associated with the perception of Christ as a lunar deity, for the lunar cycle lasts 28 days. On the lunar symbolism of Christ see: E. Tseren, *Lunnyy bog*, M., 1976 and K. Kedrov, *Poeticheskiy kosmos*, M., 1989, pp.12–13.
16. Cf. the epigraph to *Master i Margarita*.
17. See note 14.
18. Cf. my article 'O dikaryakh XX veka (Ob odnom aspekte sootnosheniya ponyatiy revolyutsii, gosudarstva i tserkvi v romane "My" E. I. Zamyatina)', *Studia Slavica Hungarica*, vol 33, No.1–4, 1987, pp.269–76.
19. An extremely interesting ending was devised by the director Peter Gothár when he adapted Bulgakov's story for the stage in May 1989 at Budapest's most famous theatre, the József Katona. As a result of a night-time encounter between Zina and Sharikov, the woman appears on stage pregnant in the final scene, so that the Professor's experiment is not without its consequences. . . In the final version of the play Gothár abandoned this ending, however.